

Ionophoretic Mobilities of some Ions from Electromigration on Paper and their Ionic Radii

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Ionophoretic mobilities of a number of cations and anions have been measured on paper after corrections for electroosmotic and tortuosity effects. From a graph obtained by plotting the experimentally determined mobilities of a number of cations and anions against their respective known ionic radii the latter for a number of anions have been estimated from their measured ionic mobilities.

The experimental procedures followed in this paper have been described in detail in an earlier communication¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present communication, free solution mobilities for SCN^- , I^- , Br^- , I_3^- , BrI_2^- , HSO_4^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$, ions in 0.1 M HClO_4 as also for orthophosphate, molybdate, tungstate and vanadate ions in alkaline medium (pH 9.54) have been determined. HSO_4^- and $[\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$ actually resulted from the conversion of SO_4^{2-} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ respectively, in the 0.1 M HClO_4 used as back ground electrolyte. Glucose was used as an electroosmotic indicator. Correction for 'added migration path length' was applied after determining R_D value for the ions. The necessary details of the instrument and its operation were discussed earlier¹.

The reagents employed for detecting the ionic species obviously depended on the ion concerned. For each of the ion studied, the best reagent was selected among several tried for the purpose. Thus, ferrocyanide and thiocyanate ions on paper were detected by spraying the strips with a dilute solution of ferric chloride. The former gave a deep blue and the latter, a deep red colour. Ferricyanide was detected by spraying the strip with a dilute solution of ferrous sulphate when a blue colour was obtained. Bromide and iodide on paper were detected by spraying the strips with a 0.1 N silver nitrate solution when pale yellow and yellow colours respectively were obtained. I_3^- and BrI_2^- were detected by starch and starch-iodide reagents respectively. Free iodine in small quantity was present but did not move with either of the species. Iodide also present in the solutions would move, may be at different speeds, but would not respond to the detecting reagents used for I_3^- and BrI_2^- .

1. M. M. Labiri, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 843.

Dichromate was detected as a red colour on paper by spraying the strip with a 1 percent solution of diphenylcarbazide in ethanol and then holding it over ammonia vapour. Sulphate was detected first by spraying the neutral paper with a 0.05 percent solution of sodium rhodizonate in water, drying it and then with a 0.02 percent aqueous BaCl_2 solution when a colourless spot on a reddish background was obtained.

In order to detect the orthophosphate ion, the chromatogram was first sprayed with a 0.4 percent (W/V) solution of ammonium molybdate in 8 percent HNO_3 and heated to about 80° , and then sprayed with 0.05 percent benzidine in 10 percent acetic acid and then exposed to ammonia vapour, when a blue spot appeared. Molybdate and tungstate were detected as blue spots by spraying the strips with a solution of stannous chloride in moderately concentrated HCl . Vanadate was detected as a yellow spot by spraying the strip with a dilute solution of sulphuric acid. The electroosmotic indicator, glucose, was detected on paper by spraying the neutral strip with an alcoholic solution of aniline oxalate and then heating it to 120° when a brown spot appeared.

For measurement of mobilities, 0.01 M solutions of potassium salts of thiocyanate, ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, dichromate, sulphate, iodide and bromide were taken in 0.1 M HClO_4 . The mobilities of Br^- , I^- , I_3^- and BrI_2^- ions were determined in 0.1 M HClO_4 as well as at $p\text{H}$ 4.03 using phthalate buffer. The results have been shown in table I.

TABLE I

Experimental conditions : Potential gradient = 3.508 volts/cm ; temp. = $23-25^\circ$; time = 30 min.

Electrolytes : 0.1 M HClO_4 Soln. and Phthalate buffer of $p\text{H}$ = 4.03

Electrolyte = 0.1 M HClO_4 Solution				Electrolyte = Phthalate buffer ($p\text{H}$ 4.03)			
Migrant	R_D value	Distance of Migration (mm)	Mobility $\times 10^4$ (Computed) ($\text{Cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$)	Migrant	R_D value	Distance of Migration (mm)	Mobility $\times 10^4$ (Computed) ($\text{Cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{Sec}$)
Glucose	0.93	2.5	...	Glucose	0.96	2.5	...
SCN^-	0.93	14.5	2.89	Br^-	0.94	16.0	3.11
$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$	0.70	12.0	3.14	I^-	0.90	16.0	3.23
HSO_4^-	1.00	14.0	2.64	BrI_2^-	0.93	15.0	2.97
$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$	1.00	19.5	3.51	I_3^-	0.90	14.0	2.87
$[\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$	1.00	10.5	2.09				
Br^-	0.97	19.5	3.61				
I^-	0.92	18.5	3.61				
BrI_2^-	0.94	19.0	3.63				
I_3^-	0.90	17.5	3.50				

Disodium salts of molybdate and tungstate and mixture of pyro and meta vanadates were prepared. For this purpose, ammonium molybdate, tungstic oxide and vanadium pentoxide were respectively dissolved in caustic soda solution, which was finally neutralised with hydrochloric acid to the requisite pH under investigation. The final solution contained an unknown but very small amount of NaCl formed during neutralisation.

Mobilities of orthophosphate, molybdate, tungstate and vanadate ions were determined as above at pH 9.54 and shown in table II. The high pH of the medium was selected on the basis of preliminary experiments to assure existence of definite.

TABLE II

Experimental conditions : Potential gradient = 5.263 volts/cm. ;
 temp. = 23 = 25° ; time = 30 min. ;
 Electrolyte : (50 ml. of 0.05 M NaHCO₃ + 5 ml. of
 0.1 M NaOH of pH = 9.54)

Migrant	Migration in electrolyte of pH = 9.54		
	R_D value	Distance of migration (mm)	Mobility $\times 10^4$ (computed) (Cm ² /V-Sec)
Glucose	0.97	2.5	...
Phosphate (HPO ₄ ⁻²)	1.00	19.5	2.33
Molybdate (MoO ₄ ⁻²)	0.96	23.0	2.80
Vanadate (HVO ₄ ⁻² + H ₂ VO ₄ ⁻)	0.86	19.0	2.60
Tungstate (WO ₄ ⁻²)	1.00	22.5	2.65

ionic species and measurable mobilities. It was also assumed that the ionic species were essentially monomeric in alkaline solutions.

Fig. 1 is the graph of ionic mobilities of some ions against their ionic radii. The data for Cu⁺², Ni⁺², Co⁺², Zn⁺², Fe⁺² used for plotting were taken from data

FIG. 1. VARIATION OF IONIC MOBILITY WITH IONIC RADIUS.

published earlier². Since in SO_4^{-2} and HPO_4^{-2} ions, the S—O and P—O bond distances determine the ionic sizes, these distances (viz., 1.73 Å and 1.508 Å respectively) have been used in the above plot. It is seen from the graph that most of these points fall on a more or less smooth curve. The ionic sizes of other ions under investigation may be estimated from this graph within a certain range of accuracy from the experimentally determined mobilities. It is seen from the graph that the points for HVO_4^{-2} and H_2VO_4^- , MoO_4^{-2} , WO_4^{-2} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{-2}$, the species having the oxygen atoms arranged tetrahedrally about the central atom are more or less close together due to the existence of the same tetrahedra. The ionic radii of these species have been obtained from the graph and shown in Table III. The ionic radii of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3}$, SCN^- , I_3^- , BrI_2^- have been similarly obtained and shown in the same Table. From figure 1, the ionic radius for MoO_4^{-2} ion is seen to be 1.80 Å, which is very close to the value of 1.83 Å for the Mo—O distance in $\text{Ag}_3\text{MoO}_4^3$.

TABLE III

Ions	Mobility $\times 10^4$ ($\text{Cm}^2/\text{V}\text{-Sec}$)	Ionic radius (Theoretical value) (Å)	Ionic radius from Figure 1 (Å)
Fe^{+3}	1.03*	0.64	
Cu^{+2}	1.68*	0.72	
Co^{+2}	1.70*	0.72	
Zn^{+2}	1.72*	0.74	
Ni^{+2}	1.78*	0.69	
Br^-	3.61	1.96	
I^-	3.61	2.20	
HPO_4^{-2}	2.33	1.56	
HSO_4^-	2.64	1.73	
$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3}$	3.51		1.96
$[\text{H}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3}$	2.09		1.34
MoO_4^{-2}	2.80		1.80
SCN^-	2.89		1.84
$\text{HVO}_4^{-2} + \text{H}_2\text{VO}_4^-$	2.60		1.70
BrI_2^-	3.63		1.96
I_3^-	3.50		1.97
WO_4^{-2}	2.65		1.73

* Taken from published data₃.

The mobilities of the anions including the complex ions, BrI_2^- , I_3^- are found to decrease regularly with increase in ionic weight. This is in agreement with the observed mobilities of ClO_3^- , BrO_3^- and IO_3^- .

2. M. M. Lahiri, and S. K. Mukherjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 980.
3. J. Donohue, and W. Shand, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 222.
4. M. Lederer, "Paper Electrophoresis", Elsevier Publishing Co., 1955, p. 15.

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